

Effectiveness of Noise Exposure and Hearing Conservation Programs among Construction Workers in Nigeria

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Abstract

The study set out to investigate the effectiveness of NEHC programs, especially among construction workers in Nigeria. This study also aims to identify barriers to the effectiveness of these programs among the target population. This group was selected because of the likelihood of their consistent exposure to high levels of noise, given the nature of their jobs. This study employed a quantitative research method with a cross-sectional design. Consequently, a questionnaire was administered to 300 construction workers in Nigeria. The data collected from these participants were analysed using SPSS software. The findings of this study showed that most participants were exposed to noise for up to 8 hours while working. Unfortunately, most of these professionals do not have NEHC programs in place by their employers. These employees were also not given hearing protective devices (HPDs) by their employers. In conclusion, this study's findings demonstrate the ineffectiveness of NEHC programs among construction workers in Nigeria. The primary reasons for this ineffectiveness are the absence of a recognisable and comprehensive NEHC program and the lack of employers providing HPDs to these workers. Consequently, this study recommended that legislation protecting construction workers in Nigeria be strengthened. Awareness programs and poverty alleviation schemes were also suggested.

Keywords: *Noise-induced hearing loss, NEHC, construction workers, Nigeria, occupational health, hearing protection.*

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Introduction

Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) remains a critical occupational health concern in industries where workers are consistently exposed to high noise levels, particularly the construction sector (Bakare, 2013; Institution of Occupational Safety and Health, 2018). Construction workers are frequently exposed to damaging noise from heavy machinery, power tools, and construction activities, often without immediate awareness of the auditory risks involved (Deaf Hear, 2016). This is mainly because the effects of noise

exposure on hearing health tend to be gradual and cumulative, leading many workers to realise the damage only after it becomes permanent or disabling (Kakavandi et al., 2021; Theodoroff & Folmer, 2015). The relationship between occupational noise exposure and hearing loss has been consistently confirmed by empirical studies (Kitcher et al., 2014; Gyamfi et al., 2016; Jariwala et al., 2017). These studies show that the duration of exposure in years significantly correlates with the degree of hearing loss among construction workers. For instance, Theodoroff and Folmer (2015) and Lie et al. (2016) found that approximately 15% of construction workers aged 20 to 69 exhibit measurable hearing loss due to prolonged noise exposure. This underscores the urgent need for preventive interventions, such as employers implementing noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs.

NEHC programs are designed to mitigate occupational noise risks through structured strategies, including the provision of hearing protection devices (HPDs), regular hearing assessments, and training on safe practices (Lewkowski et al., 2017). When properly implemented, these programs reduce the incidence of NIHL and promote overall worker health and safety (Roberts et al., 2018). In developed countries, the implementation of such programs is not only standard practice but often legally mandated, with enforceable penalties for non-compliance (Safe Work Australia, 2014; Arenas, 2014). In Nigeria, the legal framework supporting occupational hearing conservation exists. The Factories Act of 2004 mandates that employers implement programs to protect workers from harmful noise exposure (Adeze, 2021). However, the actual implementation and enforcement of these policies are often weak or inconsistent. Recent studies have highlighted that many construction companies in Nigeria either lack structured NEHC programs or implement them inadequately, leaving workers vulnerable to auditory damage (Fasola & Osisanya, 2022; Adesokan & Osisanya, 2019).

Hearing loss among construction workers in Nigeria carries not only health implications but significant socioeconomic consequences. A considerable portion of Nigeria's construction workforce comprises individuals with limited formal education who rely on their physical well-being to sustain their livelihoods (Afolabi et al., 2021). Many are breadwinners for their families, and hearing loss can compromise their employability, pushing entire households deeper into poverty (Aremu et al., 2015; Adesokan & Osisanya, 2019).

According to the World Bank, over half of Nigeria's population lives in poverty, without financial buffers or access to healthcare (The World Bank, 2020). Construction workers, particularly in informal or semi-formal employment settings, often lack job security, insurance, and severance packages (Fada & Osisanya, 2017). Once hearing loss begins to impact communication and job performance, these workers face a heightened risk of unemployment with no fallback options (Osisanya et al., 2014).

Also, access to quality healthcare, especially in rural areas where many construction projects are located, is another significant barrier (Idris & Adejumo, 2020; Ogundele & Omotosho, 2020). Even when auditory health services are available, low wages prevent workers from affording necessary care (Osisanya et al., 2014; Wouters et al., 2020). These intersecting challenges, poor policy enforcement, inadequate workplace protections, and limited healthcare access, exacerbate the risks faced by Nigerian construction workers. Effective NEHC programs can play a transformative role in this context by preventing hearing loss, supporting continued employment, and contributing to national goals such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—specifically SDG 3, which promotes good health and well-being. By evaluating the effectiveness of NEHC programs among Nigerian construction workers, this study provides policymakers, employers, and occupational health practitioners with valuable insights. It also addresses a critical gap in the literature, as there is limited empirical data on the implementation of NEHC in Nigeria. It is against this background that the study seeks to answer the question: *How effective are noise exposure and hearing conservation programs among construction workers in Nigeria?* The central aim is to assess the effectiveness of existing NEHC programs and identify factors that hinder their success. In the same vein, the study will specifically examine the effectiveness of NEHC programs among construction workers in Nigeria and identify the obstacles to their effectiveness.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional quantitative research design. Cross-sectional designs are particularly suited for assessing the prevalence and relationships among variables at a specific point in time. This approach enables the identification of associations between noise exposure, access to hearing protection, and the effectiveness of hearing conservation programs among construction workers in Nigeria.

Study Population and Setting

The study was conducted in Ikeja, Lagos State, an urban and industrial hub known for its high construction density. A total of 300 construction workers participated in the study. These participants were drawn from four construction companies operating within the area: SANA Group, Mase Contractors Limited, Laratek Ultimate Limited, and Karbak Ventures Limited.

Sampling Technique

A combination of purposive and cluster sampling techniques was used. Companies with more than 100 active construction workers were identified, and workers were then selected based on their willingness to participate. Each company contributed 75 participants, ensuring proportional representation. The minimum required sample size was calculated using Yamane's formula with a population size (N) of 2,600 and a 10% margin of error, yielding a target sample of 96. However, 300 participants were ultimately surveyed to enhance statistical power and generalizability. Again, participants were eligible if they were aged 18 years or older, actively employed as construction workers, and willing to provide informed consent. Individuals below 18, not employed in construction, or unwilling to participate were excluded.

Data Collection Tool

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, designed to capture key variables related to demographic characteristics, noise exposure, availability and use of hearing protection devices (HPDs), and the presence and effectiveness of noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs. The instrument included both closed-ended and Likert-type items, divided into six sections: participant information, demographics, noise exposure, hearing protection availability and usage, effectiveness of NEHC programs, and suggestions for improvement.

The questionnaire's reliability was assessed using a test-retest method with 10 construction workers, yielding consistent responses and confirming high reliability.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from Manchester Metropolitan University and the Lagos State Ministry of Health. Participants were informed of the study's objectives, and confidentiality and anonymity were assured. Written informed consent was obtained prior to data collection.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were used to summarize demographic variables and responses. Inferential statistics, specifically the Chi-square test, were employed to evaluate the association between the availability of NEHC programs, the provision of HPDs, and the frequency of noise exposure. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Participant Demographics

According to Table 1, 300 construction workers participated in the study. The majority were male (93.3%, n=280), with females accounting for only 6.7% (n=20). Most respondents were aged 30–39 (52.3%), followed by 40–49 (26.3%) and 50 years and above (12.7%). The workforce was relatively experienced, with 57.7% (n=173) having 1–5 years of construction experience, and 28.7% (n=86) having 6–10 years. The dominant job roles included equipment operators (25.7%), electricians (20.7%), and supervisors (20%).

Table 1. Characteristics of Research Participants

Variables	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Under 20	2	0.7
	20-29	18	6.0
	30-39	157	52.3
	40-49	79	26.3
	50 or above	38	12.7
	Prefer not to tell	6	2.0
	Total	300	100
Gender	Man	280	93.3
	Woman	20	6.7
	Prefer not to tell	0	0.0
	Total	300	100
Experience in Construction	Less than 1 year	40	13.3
	1-5 years	173	57.7
	6-10 years	86	28.7
	11-19 years	1	0.3
	Total	300	100
Primary Job Role	Labourer	1	0.3
	Carpenter	57	19.0
	Electrician	62	20.7
	Equipment Operator	77	25.7
	Supervisor	60	20.0
	Other	43	14.3
	Total	300	100
Frequency of exposure to noise	Never	23	7.7
	Occasionally	30	10.0
	Frequently	176	58.7

Noise Exposure Patterns

Noise exposure was frequent among participants (Table 2). Over half of respondents (58.7%) reported frequent exposure to loud noise at work, and 23.7% reported constant exposure. Only 7.7 indicated no exposure. Regarding duration, 47.3% of workers experienced 1–4 hours of noise exposure per day, 35% experienced 5–8 hours, and 13.7% experienced more than 8 hours. The primary sources of noise were heavy machinery (46.3) and construction activities such as drilling and hammering (33.7).

Table 2. Noise Exposure Patterns Among Construction Workers (N = 300)

Exposure Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Frequency of Noise Exposure	Never	23	7.7
	Occasionally	30	10.0
	Frequently	176	58.7

	Always	71	23.7
Daily Duration of Exposure	Less than 1 hour	12	4.0
	1–4 hours	142	47.3
	5–8 hours	105	35.0
	More than 8 hours	41	13.7
Primary Source of Loud Noise	Heavy machinery	139	46.3
	Construction activities	101	33.7
	Vehicle traffic	20	6.7
	Power tools	3	1.0
	Other	37	12.3

Availability and Use of NEHC Programs and HPDs

A critical finding was that only 9 of the respondents (n=27) acknowledged the presence of a hearing conservation program (NEHC) at their workplace (Table 3). The vast majority (91) reported that no such program existed. Among those who reported having NEHC programs, only 2.7 found them somewhat effective, while 6.3 found them ineffective. Notably, 91 did not respond to the effectiveness question because no recognized program was present.

Similarly, only nine workers reported being provided with hearing protection devices (HPDs), such as earplugs or earmuffs. Among those who did receive HPDs, usage was inconsistent, and few reported receiving training on proper usage.

Table 3. Availability and Use of NEHC Programs and Hearing Protection Devices (HPDs) (N = 300)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
NEHC Program Availability	Yes	27	9.0
	No	273	91.0
Perceived Effectiveness of NEHC Programs*	Somewhat effective	8	2.7
	Not effective	19	6.3
	Missing/No program	273	91.0
HPD Provision by Employer	Yes	27	9.0
	No	273	91.0
Use of HPDs When Provided	Always	—	—
	Frequently	—	—
	Occasionally	—	—
	Never	—	—
Training on Proper Use of HPDs	Yes	—	—
	No	—	—

Note: 91% of participants did not respond to the NEHC program effectiveness question due to the program's absence.

Chi-Square Test Results

Three key hypotheses were tested using Chi-square analyses to examine associations between the availability of NEHC programs and HPDs with noise exposure and auditory symptoms.

Table 4. Availability of NEHC Programs and Auditory Symptoms

NEHC Program	Tinnitus	Temporary Loss	Permanent Loss	Total with Symptoms
Yes	11 (68.8%)	4 (25.0%)	1 (6.2%)	16
No	83 (60.1%)	50 (36.2%)	5 (3.6%)	138
Total	94 (61.0%)	54 (35.1%)	6 (3.9%)	154

Out of the 154 participants experiencing auditory symptoms, 89.6% (n=138) were from companies without NEHC programs (Table 4). This difference was statistically significant, supporting the claim that the lack of NEHC programs is associated with a higher incidence of auditory symptoms.

Table 5. Availability of NEHC Programs and Noise Exposure Frequency

NEHC Program	Never	Occasionally	Frequently	Always	Total
Yes	16	1	6	4	27
No	5	26	179	63	273

Note: Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 124.92, p < 0.001$

The data showed that 76.2% of those with NEHC programs were never exposed to noise, whereas 88.7% of those frequently or consistently exposed worked without NEHC programs. This association was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), confirming that the availability of NEHC programs correlates with reduced exposure.

Table 6. Provision of HPDs and Noise Exposure Frequency

HPDs Provided	Never	Occasionally	Frequently	Always	Total
Yes	20	0	4	3	27
No	1	27	181	64	273

Note: Chi-square test: $\chi^2 = 205.60, p < 0.001$

Among those provided with HPDs, 74.1% reported no noise exposure, and only 11.1% were constantly exposed. Conversely, 66.3% of participants not provided with HPDs were frequently exposed to noise. This difference was also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the provision of HPDs is associated with reduced noise exposure at work.

Discussion

This study set out to evaluate the effectiveness of noise exposure and hearing conservation (NEHC) programs among construction workers in Nigeria. The findings reveal a clear and concerning gap between policy intent and practical implementation. Despite the Nigeria Factories Act of 2004 mandating employers to provide hearing protection and conservation programs, only 9% of the surveyed workers reported the presence of such programs in their workplaces. Moreover, of those who acknowledged the presence of NEHC programs, very few considered them effective. These findings strongly suggest that NEHC programs in the Nigerian construction sector are either poorly implemented or absent.

The situation becomes more critical when noise exposure levels are considered. Over 80% of participants reported frequent or constant exposure to loud noise at work, often for several hours each day. The primary sources of this exposure, heavy machinery and construction activities, are integral to the industry and difficult to avoid. Without protective measures, prolonged exposure poses a significant risk of noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL), as documented among workers in similar contexts (Kitcher et al., 2014; Aliyu et al., 2020).

The strong statistical association between the availability of NEHC programs and reduced noise exposure, as demonstrated by the Chi-square tests, provides empirical support for the importance of these programs. Workers who reported access to NEHC initiatives were significantly less likely to be frequently or constantly exposed to loud noise. Similarly, those who were provided with hearing

protection devices (HPDs) reported substantially lower exposure levels, underscoring the preventive potential of simple interventions such as earplugs or earmuffs.

These findings align with earlier studies that have emphasized the value of NEHC programs. In particular, the systematic review by Silva et al. (2022) demonstrated that HPDs significantly reduce workers' exposure to hazardous noise levels when properly used. Taye et al. (2009) also showed that workers provided with hearing protection had better auditory health outcomes than those without. This current study reaffirms these conclusions and extends their relevance to the Nigerian construction sector, where empirical data on NEHC effectiveness have been scarce.

The study also corroborates the earlier findings of Ologe et al. (2005), who reported poor adoption of hearing protection strategies among industrial workers in Nigeria. Despite that study being conducted two decades ago, the current results suggest that little progress has been made. This stagnation points to systemic issues, including weak regulatory enforcement, lack of awareness, and cost-driven reluctance among employers to invest in worker safety measures.

Beyond the health implications, the findings of this study carry serious socioeconomic consequences. Many Nigerian construction workers operate in informal or semi-formal settings with minimal job security or benefits. As prior studies have noted (Afolabi et al., 2021; Adesokan & Osisanya, 2019), these workers often lack health insurance, making them highly vulnerable when occupational illnesses or injuries occur. Hearing loss, although gradual and often invisible, can severely limit an individual's capacity to perform in noise-intensive environments, potentially leading to job loss and further impoverishment. In a country where more than half the population lives in poverty (The World Bank, 2020), the long-term costs of NIHL extend beyond the individual to entire households.

The findings also have important policy implications. First, there is an urgent need to enforce the occupational safety provisions of the Factories Act more rigorously. Employers who fail to implement NEHC programs should be held accountable. Second, there is a need for national and state-level awareness campaigns to educate both employers and workers about the risks of occupational noise exposure and the benefits of hearing conservation practices. Many workers, as suggested by Fasola and Osisanya (2022), may not fully understand the cumulative damage caused by daily exposure to high-decibel noise or how to use protective devices effectively.

Furthermore, the study highlights the need for workplace-based interventions, including mandatory provision of HPDs, regular noise monitoring, and periodic audiometric testing. These interventions are standard in developed countries and have been associated with reduced NIHL incidence (Lewkowski et al., 2017; Safe Work Australia, 2014). Implementing these measures in Nigerian construction companies, even in basic form, could drastically improve occupational health outcomes.

The study's limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design limits causal interpretation. While associations were identified between the presence of NEHC programs or HPDs and lower noise exposure, the direction of causality cannot be confirmed. Longitudinal studies would be better suited to assess the long-term effects of such programs on hearing outcomes. Second, the data relied on self-reported measures, which are susceptible to recall bias and social desirability bias. For example, workers may have underreported symptoms or overestimated their use of HPDs. Despite these limitations, the sample size was robust, and the statistical analyses were appropriate for the study objectives.

Finally, this study also reveals a substantial research gap in the Nigerian occupational health landscape. Most existing studies focus on the effects of noise exposure, with little attention given to the actual implementation and efficacy of NEHC programs. This study helps bridge that gap and offers a foundation for future research and policy development.

Conclusion

The results of this study paint a stark picture of occupational hearing health in Nigeria's construction sector. NEHC programs are largely absent, and when they do exist, they are often ineffective. Workers remain heavily exposed to harmful noise without access to basic protective measures. As Nigeria continues its push toward industrial development and urban infrastructure expansion, worker safety, particularly auditory health, must not be neglected. Strengthening policy enforcement, raising awareness, and investing in low-cost protective interventions are not just ethical imperatives but practical necessities for sustainable development.

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